

Acknowledgement

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Synthesis and Cleavage Reactions of 9-Aryl-4H,8H-pyrano[2,3-f](1,4)benzoxazin-4-one Derivatives

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A good number of 1,4-benzoxazine derivatives are reported to have biological and pharmacological activities¹⁻⁴. The condensed oxazines also possess fluorescent brightening property⁵. Many chromone derivatives act as spasmolytic agents^{6,7}. In continuation of our earlier work on fused 1,4-benzoxazines^{8,9}, we report the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of the title compounds. A few selected pyranobenzoxazine derivatives are cleaved with hydrazine hydrate to form pyrazole derivatives and their biological activity is reported.

The starting materials required for the synthesis of title compounds, 8-amino-7-hydroxy-2-methylchromone (1a) and 8-amino-7-hydroxy-2,3-dimethylchromone (1b) were prepared by adopting the methods available in literature^{10,11}. Various 9-aryl-4H,8H-pyrano[2,3-f](1,4)benzoxazin-4-ones (2) were prepared by the condensation of 2-methyl- and 2,3-dimethyl-7-hydroxy-8-aminochromones (1a, 1b) with different phenacyl bromides by refluxing in dry

acetone containing anhydrous potassium carbonate (Scheme 1). They were characterised by their analytical spectral data.

Scheme 1

A strong ir absorption band is found around 1640 cm⁻¹ for the chromone carbonyl function in all the compounds. The stretchings of C=N are observed in the region 1600-1590 cm⁻¹. The pmr spectrum of 2b displayed two singlets, at δ 3.4 (CH₃) and 5.2 (CH₃). The proton of chromone ring (C-8) absorbed at δ 6.1. The hydrogens of p-chlorophenyl nucleus appeared as two doublets at δ 7.45 and 8.41. Another pair of doublets at δ 6.9 and 7.8 are assigned to C-5 and C-6 hydrogens respectively. The molecular ion appeared at m/z 305 as the base peak in the mass spectrum of 2e. Loss of benzonitrile, recorded at m/z 103, is one of the prominent cleavages observed in the compound resulting a fragment at m/z 202. A peak at m/z 252 is assigned for the fragment formed from a cleavage involving retro-Diels-Alder reaction by the elimination of dimethyl acetylene from molecular ion. All the other prominent peaks are also accounted for.

It is interesting to note that the reaction of 2a, b, e, f with hydrazine hydrate in refluxing alcohol, cleaved the pyranone ring at ethereal oxygen which ultimately afforded 3-aryl-6-(pyrazolo-5-yl)-2H(1,4)-benzoxazin-5-ols (3a-d) as shown in Scheme 2. All the products gave deep colouration with neutral ferric chloride, indicating the cleavage of pyrone ring in 2. The structures of the compounds are assigned on the basis of their analytical and spectral properties.

Scheme 2

Ir spectra of these compounds display two bands at around 3 350 (NH) and 3 450 cm^{-1} (OH). The absorption due to the carbonyl function of pyrone ring is totally absent.

In pmr spectrum of 3a, a three-proton singlet appeared at δ 2.4 for the methyl group on pyrazole. A two-proton singlet δ 3.5 is assigned to the methylene group of oxazine nucleus. A two-proton multiplet at δ 6.4 is attributed to two aromatic protons at C-8 of benzoxazine and C-4 of pyrazole nuclei. The protons on phenyl nucleus and proton attached to C-7 appeared as a complex multiplet at δ 7.3–8.1 integrating for six protons.

The mass spectrum of 3a contained molecular ion at m/z 305 as base peak. It loses benzonitrile (m/z 103) to give a fragment at m/z 202 which eliminates 2-methylpyrazole to record at m/z 120. The base peak also suffers a loss of nitrogen molecule, commonly observed in pyrazoles, to form an ion at m/z 277. The other major fragments occurred at m/z 175 (11.2), 161 (10.0), 119 (18.7) and 108 (100.0). Physical data of the compounds are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	R'	Mol. formula	M.p.** °C	Yield %
2a	H	H	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_5$	180 ^a	56
2b	H	Cl	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClNO}_5$	210 ^a	55
2c	H	OOH ₂	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_6$	214 ^a	59
2d	H	CH ₃	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{16}\text{NO}_5$	216 ^a	51
2e	OH ₂	H	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_5$	212 ^b	48
2f	OH ₂	Cl	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClNO}_5$	188 ^a	50
2g	OH ₂	CH ₃	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_5$	221 ^c	52
3a	H	H	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	194 ^d	80
3b	H	Cl	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_5$	191 ^d	85
3c	OH ₂	H	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	196 ^d	82
3d	OH ₂	Cl	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_5$	215 ^d	81

*All compounds showed satisfactory C, H and N analyses.
**Solvent for crystallisation: ^amethanol, ^bacetone, ^cdioxan, ^dbenzene.

Biological evaluation: Five compounds of type 2 and one compound 3a, were assayed against two bacteria, *Bacillus megaterium* and *Proteus vulgaris*, following Vincent and Vincent filter paper disc method^{1,2}. The compounds were tested at 400 and 600 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations. Compounds 2a, b, e were moderately toxic towards *P. vulgaris* and ineffective against *B. megaterium*. 2c was found to lack antibacterial activity and 2d moderately active against both the bacteria. 3a was selectively toxic to *B. megaterium*.

The compounds employed for the evaluation of antibacterial activity were also used for the screening of antifungal activity against *Dreschlera speciferum* and *Fusarium solani* adopting glass-slide humid chamber technique³. The compounds were screened at 360, 600 and 840 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations. Both the fungi were sensitive towards 2a, while 2a and 2e caused more than 50% spore germination inhibition of both the fungi at 600 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ dose

level. 2b and 2d registered no toxicity, while 3a showed a moderate toxicity to both the fungi.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared 137 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a JMS-D 300 mass spectrometer.

9-Aryl-4H, 8H-pyrano[2,3-f](1,4)benzoxazin-4-ones (2a–g): A mixture of *o*-hydroxyaminochromone (1a or 1b; 0.01 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.015 mol) in dry acetone (250 ml) was stirred for 3 h at room temperature. To it was added additional anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.015 mol) and phenacyl bromide (0.01 mol) and the resultant mixture is refluxed for 24 h. It was then filtered hot, the excess acetone distilled and the residue diluted with ice-cold water (100 ml). The resulting solid was filtered, washed, dried and recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

Cleavage reaction: 9-Aryl-4H, 8H-pyrano[2,3-f](1,4)benzoxazin-4-one (2a, b, e or f; 0.005 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (99%; 2 ml) were taken in ethanol (20 ml) and refluxed for 1 h. The uniform solution thus obtained was concentrated and diluted with ice-cold water (100 ml). The resulting solid was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and purified by recrystallisation using benzene.

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